

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

O'ZBEKISTONNING TOG'LI VA TOG'LI HUDUDLARIDA YONG'OQNING QIMMAT ZANJIRI TAHLILI

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ANALYSIS OF VALUE CHAIN OF WALNUT IN MOUNTAIN AND SUB-MOUNTAIN AREAS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya

Maqolada tog' va tog'oldi hududlarida yong'oq yetishtirish va sotish qiymat zanjirida yakuniy narx shakllanishi bo'yicha xarajatlar ulushi tahlili natijalari keltirilgan. Izlanish natijalariga ko'ra dehqonlar tomonidan olingan sof qiymat, yong'oq mag'izlarini an'anaviy vositachilardan farqli o'laroq, takomillashgan kanal ichidagi qayta ishlovchilar orqali sotilganlarida sezilarli o'sishni ko'rsatadi.

Abstract

This study shows the results of the cost share analysis of the final price formation in the value chain of walnut production and sale in mountain and sub-mountain regions in Uzbekistan. Results revealed that net price received by the farmers shows a significant increase when the walnut kernels are sold through improved in-channel processors as opposed to traditional intermediaries.

Kalit so'zlar: Yong'oq, dehqon, qiymat zanjiri, sotuvchi, sotuv samaradorligi, qayta ishlovchi, marketing samaradorligi, eksport.

Keywords: walnut, farmer, value chain, trader, marketing margin, processor, marketing efficiency, export.

INTRODUCTION

The post-harvest losses in this fruit are significant in terms of quantity and resultant economic value. The concept of placing emphasis on increased production of fruits is self-defeating. It is important to see how the produce goes through processing and finally reaches the export market. Efforts should be made to integrate production with post-harvest management to improve its availability by reducing its losses[1]. Walnut (Juglans regia) production in Uzbekistan is one of the important horticultural products being exported to almost 50 countries generating nearly 30 thousand metric tonnes annually. Walnut, the second most important nut, is found in areas with more moisture either in pure walnut forests or mixed with fruit trees. There are 30 traditional walnut varieties native to Uzbekistan. Walnut forests supply approximately 90 tons of walnuts each year. Although they are only harvested for one month, they contribute greatly to the annual income of rural communities. In 2020, farmers could sell walnuts for a price of US\$2 per kg. [2]

Walnut holds a good place in trade owing to its high demand in national and international market. However, the poor marketing system has deprived growers from the benefits that actually should accrue to them. Processing of this fruits at farm level could be an option for such problems but inadequate and unscientific processing resulted in qualitative loss, which is more serious and can infected the produce unsuitable for human consumption[3].

Although number of references relating to estimation of post-harvest losses and value addition in several fruits are available in literature [4], a very little work

has been done regarding walnut in Uzbekistan. Realizing the economic importance of walnut, this paper investigated into the analysis of losses, and modernized value chain of walnut in several regions of Uzbekistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was based on the data collected through questionnaires conducted in 2023 from walnut farmers in five districts of Samarkand region - Urgut, Ishtikhan, Oqdaryo, Kushrabot, Payariq and Forish district of Jizzakh region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the mountainous and sub-mountainous regions of Uzbekistan, the walnut value chain consists of the following links:

1. Cultivation: Walnut cultivation in these regions is often carried out in places with suitable climate and soil conditions. Farmers plant walnut seedlings, carry out necessary care such as watering, fertilizing, pest control. Terraced farming methods can be used to optimize land use in mountainous areas.

2. Harvesting: Walnut harvesting in the region usually begins on August 20, when the walnuts are fully ripe in the fall. Traditionally, manual harvesting methods are used, with workers climbing trees to shake branches or using long sticks to tap the nuts. Ripe nuts are picked and prepared for further processing. Early harvesting of walnuts, between August 20 and 30, allows obtaining high-value light-colored kernels, but also increases the percentage of low-value "puchak" kernels.

3. Post-harvest processing: Post-harvest processing includes shelling, washing and drying of the walnuts. In mountainous areas, traditional methods of

debarking can be used, such as using wooden mallets or stone mills to remove the green outer casing. Drying is usually done naturally, by drying in the sun or using well-ventilated drying rooms.

4. **Preparation:** In mountainous and semi-mountainous areas, walnut preparation may involve local merchants or middlemen who collect walnuts from farmers and transport them to their markets. Transportation methods may include trucks or other vehicles suitable for use in mountainous terrain.

5. **Processing:** after drying, the walnuts are processed to separate them from the husks (bites). Depending on the size and available equipment, this can be done manually or with the help of mechanical grinding machines. This part is usually not done by the farmers, but by the preparers with the help of hired workers.

6. **Packaging:** After the walnuts are processed, they are packaged for storage, transportation and distribution. Packaging materials can vary, but commonly used options include cardboard boxes or plastic containers. The packaging is designed to protect the walnut from damage and preserve its quality during transportation.

7. **Retail:** At the retail level, walnuts from the mountainous regions of Uzbekistan can be sold at local farmers' markets. These outlets serve both local consumers and tourists interested in purchasing local products. In addition, attention can be paid to promoting the unique qualities and origin of mountain walnuts to attract buyers.

8. **Export.** When exporting walnuts from Uzbekistan, several general requirements are usually applied:

- **Quality standards:** Products intended for export must meet international trade regulations and quality standards set by the importing country. Nuts must be of good quality, free from pests, diseases and contaminants.

- **Packaging and labelling:** Walnuts for export must be properly packed and labeled in accordance with international standards and established national requirements. Proper packaging helps protect nuts during shipping and keeps them fresh.

- **Phytosanitary certificate:** Many countries require a phytosanitary certificate to ensure that exported walnuts are free from harmful pests and diseases.

- **Export license and documentation:** Exporters must obtain the necessary export license and complete all documentation requirements according to the country's export regulations. This includes invoices, customs declarations, certificates of origin and

additional documents requested by the importing country.

- **Trade agreements and tariffs:** If there is any trade agreement between Uzbekistan and the importing country, special tariff rates or preferential trade conditions affecting the export process may be applied.

Currently, the commodity characteristics (consumer value) of walnuts in the world market are evaluated by the following indicators:

- Taste quality of walnut kernel
- Color of walnut core
- An indicator of the size of the kernel of walnut
- The thickness of a walnut shell
- Ease of separating the kernel from the shell

According to Inobatov [5], walnuts are offered to the Russian market in the following categories, depending on the size of the kernel:

1. **Halves.** The kernel of the walnut is divided into two equal parts and looks like a butterfly. It is consumed directly as a ready-made food product. This category includes walnuts, 80% of which are halves, as well as a kernel the size of three-quarters of a halves, the rest of the mass consists of quarters.

2. **Quarters.** These are pieces of the kernel that have not been sifted into a sieve with round holes and a diameter of 11 mm. The walnut kernel is divided into four equal parts. It is eaten directly and added to various dishes and salads

3. **Eights, small pieces of kernel.** This discharge of the kernel consists of pieces that have passed through a sieve with round holes and a diameter of 11 mm, but at the same time not sifted into a sieve with a diameter of 3 mm. Eights are usually divided into two sizes: 3-6 mm and 7-10 mm. These pieces of walnut are used in confectionery and baking.

4. **Crumbs.** These are tiny pieces of the walnut kernel, the size of which does not exceed 3 mm. The crumb is used in the confectionery craft, namely: it is added to the dough, ice cream, cakes, pastries are sprinkled, and walnut fillers are prepared from the crumb.

5. **Walnut flour.** The smallest part of the nut kernel that has passed through a sieve. It is added to the dough and used to prepare cakes, various pastries and nut cream.

Products in each category are sold for a specific purpose based on market demand, and the product price is formed accordingly. There is a significant difference in grades between categories. Also, the products of the first and second (mainly the first) categories are sold at different prices depending on the color of the kernel.

Table 1

Classification of walnut kernels in the local market in Uzbekistan according to color and shape

Kernel class	Description	Color	Average purchase price (2022, thousand soums)
G'ilak	Mainly aimed at domestic consumption	White	65
		Brown	58
		Red	43
Kapalak	Intended for export and partly for domestic consumption.	White	55
		Brown	51
		Mixed	46
		Red	45
Sechka	As a raw material for confectionery products	Brown	26
		Mixed	26
		Red	26
		Black	26
Puchak	As a raw material for confectionery products	Brown	21
		Mixed	21
		Red	21
		Black	21

Table 2

Classification of unshelled walnuts for export by size

Grade name	Code	Nut size
Apple	111	33-38 mm
Pear	555	30-33 mm
Cherry	999	27-30 mm

According to the international classification, walnut kernels are divided into the following types:

- | | |
|-----------------------|--------|
| 1. Extra light half | 1st |
| 2. Light halves | Second |
| 3. Light broken | Third |
| 4. Light amber halves | Fourth |
| 5. Light amber broken | Fifth |

During the research, questionnaires were conducted among walnut growers in Urgut, Ishtikhan, Oghdarya, Kushrabort, Payariq districts of Samarkand region and Farish district of Jizzakh region. All costs and revenues in the analysis are calculated relative to the processors' purchase prices. The pattern of use of

walnut by surveyed farmers showed that the weight of commodity products is 92.39 percent of the gross walnut production of each farm. Losses make up 7.52% of the total nut production. Only 1.3 percent of the gross nut production was saved for family consumption.

Table 3

Realization of walnut harvest in the surveyed farms

Indicators	Quantity, tons	% of total
Total product	1740	100,00
Losses	130,8	7,52
Consumption	22,6	1,30
Marketable surplus	1586,5	91,18

Producers in the study area used two channels to sell their products:

1st channel: Farmer → Trader → Processor → Export

2nd channel: Farmer → Processor → Export

The practice of selling small quantities of unshelled walnuts at local farmers' markets was also observed. When the product is delivered through the traditional channel, farmers sell their produce in the form

of unshelled walnuts to middlemen who go door-to-door in villages. They, in turn, sell the product to the processors, either in a cracked or cracked form. In the improved channel, farmers sell their products directly to the processor. Adding value to products and processing plays a major role in the walnut value chain. Improving this chain is important in adding value to it and distributing it equally across all links of the production and supply chain.

1- picture. Walnut supply chain.

Capital Formation and Investment Pattern

Most of the walnut growers in Uzbekistan belong to the category of peasant farms operating in remote areas and working in the market with a small profit. At the same time, value addition for the export of walnuts requires a large amount of technical equipment and manpower.

Many private enterprises have invested in walnut processing, and they spend a lot of money on fixed and

working capital to produce products for the foreign market [6]. As can be seen from table 4, investments in buildings occupy a high weight in the formation of total capital. The most important objects of investment by weight are conveyor belts (14.93%), followed by dryers (3.45%), boxes (3.54%) and core graders (1.74%). This capital stock requires regular technical service and repair.

Table 4

Capital formation at private walnut enterprises

Capital formation	Quantity (pcs)	Value (thousand soums)	% of total value
<i>Working capital</i>			
Boxes	2530	106638	3,54
Buckets	755	25271	0,84
Washing tubs	65	2916	0,1
Others (hammers, washing baskets, etc.)	672	3610	0,12
Sub-total (a)	4022	138574	4,60
<i>Medium-term capital</i>			
Tractor/load carrier	0,5	20411	0,68
Vacuum packers	2	37073	1,23
Semi vacuum packer	0,5	15551	0,52
Walnut grader	1	32630	1,08
Kernel grader	2	52486	1,74
Transformer (stabilizer)	1	21661	0,72
Tray dryers	6,5	106638	3,54
Conveyer belts	3	449880	14,93
Blowers	1,5	5554	0,19
Strapping machine	1,5	16246	0,54
Taping machine	1,5	5554	0,19
Other (trolleys, sealers and hand graders)	4,5	5276	0,18
Sub-total (b)	25,5	769240	25,52
<i>Long term capital</i>			
Land / buildings	4	2082780	69,1
Washing tanks	4	23327	0,77
Sub-total (c)	—	2106107	69,88
Total(a+b+c)	4051,5	3013922	100

Several raw material delivers from walnut growers in different districts, while one processing company was found to have established its own walnut plantation. The total purchase of walnuts and kernels ranged from 1000-3000 to 2500-3500 centners. Although the main part of walnuts was purchased from Forish (23%), followed by Ishtikhan (20%), Urgut (18%), Akdarya (10%) and others (29%), the largest amount of walnut kernels share (42%) was prepared from Ishtikhon district and Akdarya district (30%). As for value-added walnut exports, most of the product was exported through agents. 47 percent of the product was exported directly to other walnut importing countries, mainly in the form of kernels.

The nut supply chain is shown in Figure 1. The fruits are mostly harvested when the tree begins to split its bark and some nuts begin to fall naturally. Harvesting begins on August 15-20 in the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan, and on September 10-15 in mountain and sub-mountain regions.

A common harvesting practice is to beat the bearing branches with long sticks. The harvest is usually collected by women and children. When the crop is knocked down, 50-60% of the peel is removed if the nut crop is ripe, and 2-3% of the peel is removed if the crop is raw. The harvested crop is spread out in a shady and windy place for ethylene synthesis and stored for 3-4 days to separate the husk. It is quickly and qualitatively peeled by hand. Nowadays, due to the development of technology, this work can be done using machines, but in this way, the quality of the crop is damaged. Bleaching of the nuts is also used to some extent in some regions. In this case, the crop is harvested before it is ripe, the harvested crop is separated from the husk within 2-3 days and dried in a place away from the wind and sunlight. But in this process, the raw product loses up to 30% weight in 24 hours. The nut crop is dried in open conditions and may take 3-5 days to dry depending on favorable weather conditions.

Processing entrepreneurs organize the collection of products from nut growers in different regions, in the process of buying walnuts from farmers, they are priced according to the moisture level of the nuts, the color of the kernel, the thickness and thinness of the shell, and the type of color. Dried walnuts are packed and stored in a place where there is no sunlight. If it is not free from sunlight, it will negatively affect the quality of the crop and lead to a decrease in the value of the product. Private enterprises purchase raw materials directly from farmers with partial or full advance payment.

It was observed that the studied walnut farmers preferred to sell the product to processing enterprises. Quick payments and high prices have led to farmers making good profits by bypassing middlemen.

After the product is brought and unloaded by the farmer or the entrepreneur in the processing plants, the product is subjected to quality control. Walnut size, kernel percentage and shell thickness as well as nut moisture, color, flavor are used to determine price and add value. Then the walnuts are graded by size using a

grader. It is desirable to obtain full-sized kernels; walnuts are soaked in washing tanks for 6-10 hours for removing dirt, other contamination and for easy cracking. Soaked walnuts are then cracked by skilled female workers with the help of wooden hammers and steel coils. Skilled women labours are engaged for cracking nuts so as to avoid breakage of kernels. About 37-40 kg of kernels are obtained from 100 kg of nuts depending upon shell thickness and quality of nuts. After extraction from the nuts, the kernels are dried in tray dryers and 5-10% moisture is kept inside the kernel. Then kernels undergo grading by kernel graders depending upon size. The graded produce is then placed over conveyor belts and skilled labour sort them out on the basis of kernel colour into five grades as per Table 2. During summers, in lean season, kernels are preserved with nitrogen and packed in vacuum silver packs to get over unfavourable climatic conditions. After this, the produce is prepared for final packing during peak season. Summer packs are opened and finally packed into plastic packs of varying size. Packed material is then put into corrugated boxes. Packed material is then put into corrugated boxes. The containers are fumigated with methyl Bromide to prevent any access of fungus inside it.

The exporter must obtain another certificate confirming that the fumigation has been carried out in accordance with the prescribed standards and that the fumigation has been carried out in the container and not before varnishing, painting or wrapping[7]. The packaged nut kernels are then exported to various trading partners.

Value addition for export when procured as nut and exported as kernel by processor.

Under the conditions of Uzbekistan, within these channels, walnut processing enterprises purchase walnuts from merchants or directly from local farmers. Processors compensate these suppliers in the form of prices based on the quality of the walnuts. In determining the price of the harvested product, processors classify purchased nuts into three distinct varieties (Table 2). Processors devote considerable resources to increasing the value of walnuts and then releasing them to the global export market in the form of different kernel varieties. Although processor categorize kernel into 5 grades, however, price spread for grade viz. Light halves, Light broken, and Light amber halves has been averaged and presented in Table 5. It is noteworthy that when farmers are able to sell their products directly to processors, their net income increases significantly. In addition, all intermediaries involved in this direct sales channel prior to the processor have improved profit margins compared to traditional sales channels. Although proportional costs and revenues are relatively high for recyclers, their profit margins remain the highest. This suggests that each unit of value-added investment serves as a proxy for quality improvement in the value-added process[8]. In addition, the distribution of various cost components invested by processing enterprises shows that most of the costs are directed to fixed capital and export of products to international markets.

Table 5

Distribution of the price of kernels purchased in the form of unshelled nuts in sales channels by value chain links

	Grade-I			Grade-II			Grade-III			
	Channell-I	Channell-II	Channell-I	Channell-II	Channell-I	Channell-II	Channell-I	Channell-II	%	
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	
<i>Farmer's level</i>										
Harvesting charge	466	0.58	466	0.58	403	0.6	403	0.6	261	0.65
Assembling charge	104	0.13	104	0.13	87	0.13	87	0.13	56	0.14
Dehulling	56	0.07	56	0.07	54	0.08	54	0.08	32	0.08
Cost of weight loss	128	0.16	128	0.16	114	0.17	114	0.17	72	0.18
Drying charge	72	0.09	72	0.09	67	0.11	67	0.11	44	0.11
Packing charge	48	0.06	48	0.06	40	0.06	40	0.06	28	0.07
Local charge	32	0.04	32	0.04	27	0.04	27	0.04	16	0.04
Transport charge	0	0	88	0.11	0	0	74	0.11	0	0
Miscellaneous charges	16	0.02	16	0.02	13	0.02	13	0.02	8	0.02
Total cost	923	1.15	1012	1.26	798	1.19	872	1.23	518	1.29
Loss	104	0.13	177	0.22	87	0.13	154	0.23	56	0.14
Sale price	9066	11.29	17473	21.76	7844	11.69	15118	22.53	5123	12.76
Net price	8046	10.02	16285	20.28	6958	10.37	14091	21	4545	11.32
<i>Trader's level</i>										
Purchasing price	9066	11.29	---	---	7844	11.69	---	---	5123	12.76
Collection from various places	24	0.03	---	---	20	0.03	---	---	16	0.04
Loading and unloading	8	0.01	---	---	7	0.01	---	---	4	0.01
Transport charge	88	0.11	---	---	74	0.11	---	---	48	0.12
Total cost	112	0.14	---	---	101	0.15	---	---	64	0.16
Loss	128	0.16	---	---	107	0.16	---	---	72	0.18
Sale price of nut	17827	22.2	---	---	15420	22.98	---	---	10074	25.09
Margm	8520	10.61	---	---	7368	10.98	---	---	4814	11.99
<i>Processor's level</i>										
Purchase price	17827	22.2	17473	21.76	15118	22.98	15118	22.53	10074	25.09
Assembling from growers	48	0.06	48	0.06	40	0.06	40	0.06	28	0.07
Loading	8	0.01	8	0.01	7	0.01	7	0.01	4	0.01
Unloading	8	0.01	8	0.01	7	0.01	7	0.01	4	0.01
Quality check	8	0.01	8	0.01	7	0.01	7	0.01	4	0.01
Walnut grading	16	0.02	16	0.02	13	0.02	13	0.02	8	0.02
Soaking	16	0.02	16	0.02	13	0.02	13	0.02	8	0.02
Cracking	56	0.07	56	0.07	47	0.07	47	0.07	32	0.08
Cost of conversion	241	0.3	241	0.3	208	0.31	208	0.31	137	0.34
Drying of kernel	8	0.01	8	0.01	7	0.01	7	0.01	4	0.01
Mechanical grading of kernel	8	0.01	8	0.01	7	0.01	7	0.01	4	0.01
Colour sorting	169	0.21	169	0.21	148	0.22	148	0.22	96	0.24
Packing	233	0.29	233	0.29	201	0.3	201	0.3	132	0.33
Carton	145	0.18	145	0.18	127	0.19	127	0.19	80	0.2
Aluminium foil	96	0.12	96	0.12	87	0.13	87	0.13	56	0.14
Tape	48	0.06	48	0.06	40	0.06	40	0.06	24	0.06
Fumigation of container	8	0.01	8	0.01	7	0.01	7	0.01	4	0.01
Delivery to airport/station	273	0.34	273	0.34	235	0.35	235	0.35	153	0.38
Delivery to import country	554	0.69	554	0.69	476	0.71	476	0.71	313	0.78
Export costs	48	0.06	48	0.06	40	0.06	40	0.06	24	0.06
Miscellaneous charges	32	0.04	32	0.04	27	0.04	27	0.04	16	0.04
Cost of fixed capital	8054	10.03	8054	10.03	6965	10.38	6965	10.38	4549	11.33
Cost of fixed capital	10062	12.53	10062	12.53	8703	12.97	8703	12.97	5685	14.16
Loss	1566	1.95	1566	1.95	1208	1.8	1208	1.8	731	1.82
Export price	80300	100	80300	100	67100	100	67100	100	40150	100

Value addition for export when procured as kernel and exported by processor

In the modernized channel, the processor appears as one of the important functions between producers and consumers. In this case processor purchased better quality kernels either from trader or directly from farmer. and systematically process them into kernels for international markets based on global demand for kernels.

Net return to farmer was better in channel where he is able to sell his produce to processor directly even when his costs were more. In similar manner, margins of trader were more when he sold walnuts as kernel

than nuts. To sum up, net return to farmers were maximum in absolute term in modernized channels. Farmer's returns were relatively more when they sell their produce directly to processor. Further it was observed that farmer per soum invested on value addition added to the dividends of investor. Farmer's net returns were higher in absolute and proportionate terms when they sell kernels directly to the processor. Accordingly, marketing efficiency was found more in channels II when the processor purchase nuts and same results are found in channel II when processor purchase kernels from the producer. The marketing margins were more when processors acted as the main functionaries in the channel.

Distribution of the price of walnuts purchased in the form of kernels in the sales channels by value chain links

	Grade- I			Grade- II			Grade- III		
	Channel-II	Channel-I	Channel-II	Channel-I	Channel-II	Channel-I	Channel-II	Channel-I	Channel-II
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%
	<i>Farmer's level</i>								
Harvesting charge	466	0.58	466	0.58	403	0.6	261	0.65	261
Assembling charge	104	0.13	104	0.13	87	0.13	56	0.14	56
Dehulling			0						
Cost of weight loss	56	0.07	56	0.07	54	0.08	32	0.08	32
Drying charge	128	0.16	128	0.16	114	0.17	72	0.18	72
Local charge	72	0.09	72	0.09	67	0.1	44	0.11	44
Pre cracking charge	32	0.04	32	0.04	27	0.04	16	0.04	16
Cracking charge	859	1.07	859	1.07	745	1.11	486	1.21	486
Cost of conversion	658	0.82	658	0.82	570	0.85	373	0.93	373
Grading charge	2064	2.57	2064	2.57	1785	2.66	1168	2.91	1168
Packing charge	329	0.41	329	0.41	289	0.43	185	0.46	185
Transport charge	185	0.23	185	0.23	161	0.24	104	0.26	104
Miscellaneous charges	0	0	185	0.23	0	0	0	0	0
Loss	16	0.02	16	0.02	13	0.02	8	0.02	8
Sale price	4111	5.12	4304	5.36	3556	5.3	2325	5.79	2429
Net price	891	1.11	1261	1.57	778	1.16	458	1.14	787
	<i>Traders' level</i>								
Purchasing price	35035	43.63			37.87			37.86	
Collection from various places	24	0.03			20	0.03		0.04	
Loading and unloading	8	0.01			7	0.01		0.01	
Transport charge	169	0.21			148	0.22		0.24	
Total cost	201	0.25			174	0.26		0.28	
Loss	490	0.61			436	0.65		1.09	
Sale price	48750	60.71			39978	59.58		60.63	
Margin	13033	16.23			13957	20.8		21.29	
	<i>Processor's level</i>								
Purchase price	48750	60.71	48485	60.38	98125	59.58	39804	59.32	24343
Assembling from growers	48	0.06	48	0.06	106	0.06	40	0.06	28
Loading	8	0.01	8	0.01	20	0.01	7	0.01	4
Unloading	8	0.01	8	0.01	20	0.01	7	0.01	4
Quality check	8	0.01	8	0.01	20	0.01	7	0.01	4
Drying of kernel	8	0.01	8	0.01	12.8	0.01	7	0.01	4
Mechanical grading of kernel	8	0.01	8	0.01	21.23	0.01	7	0.01	4
Colour sorting	169	0.21	169	0.21	360	0.22	148	0.22	96
Packing	233	0.29	233	0.29	494	0.3	201	0.3	132
Carton	145	0.18	145	0.18	305	0.19	127	0.19	80
Aluminium foil	96	0.12	96	0.12	209	0.13	87	0.13	56
Tape	48	0.06	48	0.06	96	0.06	40	0.06	24
Fumigation of container	8	0.01	8	0.01	12	0.01	7	0.01	4
Delivery to airport/station	273	0.34	273	0.34	572	0.35	235	0.35	153
Delivery to import country	554	0.69	554	0.69	1173	0.71	476	0.71	313
Export costs	48	0.06	48	0.06	96	0.06	24	0.06	24
Miscellaneous charges	32	0.04	32	0.04	60	0.04	27	0.04	16
Cost of fixed capital	8054	10.03	8054	10.03	17100	10.38	6965	10.38	4549
Cost of fixed capital	9740	12.13	9740	12.13	20677.03	12.56	8428	12.56	5501
Loss	1445	1.8	1445	1.8	3211.45	1.95	1308	1.95	803
Export price	80300	100	80300	100	67100	100	40150	100	40150

Accordingly, efficiency was higher in channel 2 when the processor purchased unshelled walnuts, and the same results were observed in channel 2 when the processor purchased kernels from the producer.

Net price received by farmer is more when farmer sold kernels through processor in modernized channel rather than other. In modernized channel, more marketing cost was incurred by processor which adds value to the produce and reduces the loss in kernels processing. Despite, more marketing cost in modernized channel processor's margins were seemed to be less which in turn is favourable for the producer to sale its produce

through modernized channel. Marketing efficiency was also seen more in case of modernized channel, which emphasized upon the need for grading and scientific manipulation of surplus. Through value addition, integration of walnut production with export marketing would help in harnessing the potential of this crop in domestic and global trade.

The net price earned by farmers shows a significant increase when the walnut kernels are sold through improved in-channel processors as opposed to traditional traders. Through the integration of value addition

and export marketing, the potential of walnut production can be effectively exploited for both domestic and international trade. At the same time, there are a number of problems in the entire process from product preparation to walnut export. Among the problems highlighted by exporters, insufficient supply of raw materials for value addition is a significant problem[9]. Despite the high demand for walnuts in the national and international markets, domestic production is insufficient to meet the demand, which leads to an imbalance between supply and demand. Lack of skilled labor, such as certified specialists and suboptimal export advisory services, as well as the absence of organic certification agencies near production centers, exacerbate the problem. In addition, the high cost of institutional loans and subsidies and the delay in utilization are creating serious problems for private enterprises.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis, we can make the following suggestions:

It is necessary to support the organization of training programs for walnut growers and the development of human resources. Most of the activities under "Production Support" do not directly address the nut production system. Although these activities are primarily aimed at increasing the area and productivity of horticultural crops, only a limited number of initiatives are aimed at developing walnut production in the region. Integration of value-added walnut production with export marketing will help use the potential of this crop in domestic and global trade. In addition, improving the quality of research in these areas will be of great benefit.

Special attention to quality improvement will also help to sell nut products at better prices in world markets.

It is necessary to establish small processing units at the producer and regional level. In addition, the government should strengthen various institutions to provide cheap and easy credit to farmers and private nut processors.

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